

Inorganic base assisted synthesis of sodium [*tris*-(acetylacetonato)nickelate(II)] complex and kinetics of its acid-dissociation

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Abstract : Nickel(II) complexes of acetylacetonate are potential materials in all disciplines notably catalysis and biology. Most of them are not easy to prepare. A synthetic method of preparation and isolation of sodium salt of *tris*-(acetylacetonato)nickelate(II), $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ and study of its stability in aqueous and acidic media have been reported. The complex has been characterized by conductance, elemental and metal analysis, UV-Vis and IR spectroscopy studies. Conductance measurement supported that the complex is 1 : 1 electrolyte. Elemental and metal analysis evidenced the presence of three units of acac (= acetylacetonato) per complex and one nickel atom [19.32% (Calcd. 20.03)] per acac unit, respectively. UV-Vis absorbance bands : ${}^3A_{2g}({}^3F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}({}^3F)$ ($\nu_1 = 9416 \text{ cm}^{-1}$); ${}^3A_{2g}({}^3F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}({}^3F)$ ($\nu_2 = 1605 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the *tris*-complex (azide assisted) are blue shifted in comparison with *trans*- $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, revealing strong Ni^{II}-acac covalent interaction. IR spectra of *tris*-complex reveal that the *tris*-complex has no coordinated water molecules. The spectra provided $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{O})$ bands at 1590 and 433 cm^{-1} which are red and blue shifted, respectively in comparison with *trans*- $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, indicating strong Ni-O bonding. The *tris*-complex is susceptible to dissociates in aqueous medium ($k_{\text{obs}} = 4.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) as well as in acid media ($k_s = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$). To comprehend the potentiality of Ni^{II}-complexes of acetylacetonate, the as-synthesized *tris*-complex must be a futuristic material.

Keywords : Nickel(II), acetylacetonate, *tris*-complex, stability, dissociation constant.

Introduction

Nickel(II) complexes of acetylacetonate (acacH) have been extensively studied because of their potential application in the field of catalysis : polymerization, oligomerization, reduction, cross-coupling, oxidation, conjugate addition to multiple bonds, rearrangements¹⁻⁶, and so on. They are found in different forms : square planar mononuclear, $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$, octahedral trinuclear, $\text{Ni}_3(\text{acac})_6$, dinuclear, $\text{Ni}_2(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and mononuclear, *trans*- $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ in solid state as well as in non-coordinating solvents. Moreover, all complexes are solvated to mononuclear *cis/trans*- $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{Solv})_2$ in coordinating solvents (Solv. = H_2O , MeOH, EtOH, DMF, DMSO, etc.). Single crystal X-ray studies of some solvent adduct complexes so far isolated in the solid state are mainly *trans*-adducts, such as *trans*- $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{MeOH})_2$ ⁷ and *trans*- $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{EtOH})_2$ ⁸. Crystal structures of square planar mononuclear, $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ ⁹ and octahedral trinuclear, $\text{Ni}_3(\text{acac})_6$ ¹⁰ had also been studied and reported. The

trinuclear species is stable in non-coordinating solvents^{11,12} whereas it is converted to mononuclear and dinuclear species in coordinating solvents, such as methanol and pyridine^{7,13}.

Another class of compounds known as homoleptic anion coordination compounds with acetylacetonate ligand have been scarcely studied¹⁴⁻¹⁹. Three nickel(II)-complexes of this class have been reported so far^{14,18,19}. The first compound based on the $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]^-$ anion was reported by Watson and Lin¹⁴ with the formula $\text{Ag}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3] \cdot 2\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Atencio *et al.*¹⁸ reported the crystal structure of $\text{K}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3] \cdot 0.3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Recently, Baldo *et al.*¹⁹ described the crystal structure of polymeric chain compound, $[\text{NaNi}(\text{acac})_3]_n$. Authors of the last two compounds showed polymeric 1D array with K/Na---O interactions between the K^+/Na^+ ions and the O atoms on opposite faces of the NiO_6 octahedron of the complex anion. Baldo *et al.*¹⁹ had got the compound, $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ as a secondary product from the methanolic solution of a mixture :

Ni(acac)₂, L-histidine, sodium *tert*-butoxide and sodium azide by following slow evaporation method for three weeks with very low yield. Undoubtedly the afore-discussed fact reveals that there is no clear-cut methodology for the synthesis of homoleptic [Ni(acac)₃]⁻ complex-ion. In this paper we report a very convenient method of preparation of sodium salt of *tris*-(acetylacetonato)nickelate(II), Na[Ni(acac)₃] with attractive yield from *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] using different inorganic bases : N₃⁻ (azide), NO₂⁻ (nitrite) and NO₃⁻ (nitrate). In addition, the dissociation reaction of the anionic complex in acid media including water has been studied spectrophotometrically.

Experimental

Materials, methods and instruments :

All chemicals were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. Sodium acetate, trihydrate (CH₃COONa.3H₂O) (Merck), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) (Merck), sodium nitrite (Merck), hydrochloric acid (Merck), sodium nitrate (Himedia), NiSO₄.6H₂O (Himedia), sodium azide (Central Drug House (P.) Ltd.), acetylacetone (Sisco Research Lab. (P.) Ltd.) were purchased from the sources mentioned in the parenthesis and used as received. All solvents were of A.R. grade and used for synthesis and spectroscopic studies. All the glassware were washed thoroughly with distilled water and dried in an oven. For the kinetic studies double distilled water was used.

UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-Vis-1800 spectrophotometer using quartz cell with a path length of 1 cm. Conductance of all the solutions was measured using a TANCO digital conductivity meter. The IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8000 FTIR spectrophotometer in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹ using pressed pellet sampling technique with KBr disc. pH of all the solution was measured using the digital pH-meter (Systronics).

The kinetics of dissociation reactions of the complexes, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and Na[Ni(acac)₃] (azide assisted) in aqueous medium with/without acid-catalyzed were followed at 25.0 ± 0.2 °C using the UV-Vis spectropho-

tometer. Absorbance versus time data were collected at 639 and 623 nm for the dissociation reaction of *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and Na[Ni(acac)₃] (azide assisted), respectively. Pseudo-first order conditions were maintained by using at least 10-fold excess of acid in each run, [complex] = 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol/dm³ and [acid] = (1.0 × 10⁻³–5.0 × 10⁻²) mol/dm³ (I = 0.2 mol/dm³ HCl + NaCl). Plots of -ln (A_t - A_∞) versus time were linear and gave the k_{obs} values. The A_∞ values for the absorbance were measured in each case after 10 half-lives. The mean percentage standard deviations for rate constants from individual runs are ±1% for k_{obs}.

Preparation of diaquobis-(acetylacetonato)nickel(II), [Ni^{II}(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] :

This compound was prepared following the modified method outlined by Charles and Pawlikowski²⁰. Acetylacetone (5.82 g, 58.13 mmol) was taken in a 100 mL beaker and small amount of water (~40 mL) was added with stirring for 10–15 min. To the solution, aqueous nickel sulphate hexahydrate (NiSO₄.6H₂O) (7.64 g, 29.06 mmol) solution was added with stirring for 30–35 min. To the resultant mixture, concentrated solution of NaOH (2 M) was added dropwise with stirring until complete precipitation. The blue-green coloured residue obtained was then filtered off and washed with cold water and then with methanol-water mixture (5 : 2, v/v) several times and dried over in air. Yield : 92%. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₈O₆Ni (FW 292.97) : C, 40.99; H, 6.21; O, 32.77. Found (%) : C, 40.67; H, 6.18; O, 31.98. Decomposition point : 220 °C.

Synthesis of sodium tris(acetylacetonato)nickelate(II), tris-Na[Ni^{II}(acac)₃] (tris-A) :

To a methanolic solution of [Ni^{II}(acac)₂(H₂O)₂], (0.5 g, 1.695 mmol) (25 ml), sodium azide (0.275 g, 4.238 mmol) dissolved in minimum amount of water was added dropwise with vigorous stirring. The mixture was then warmed on steam bath for 30 min. A light blue colour precipitation which was started to form almost immediately was completed within few minutes. It was cooled down at room temperature. The precipitate was filtered off and washed with methanol-water (1 : 3, v/v) mixture thoroughly. The precipitate was then dried in air. Yield :

75%. Calcd. for Na[C₁₅H₂₁O₆Ni] (FW 378.69) : C, 47.54; H, 5.58; O, 25.33. Found (%) : C, 47.01; H, 5.49; O, 25.01. The nickel content was determined titrimetrically following the method as described in Quantitative Vogel²¹ and was found to be 19.32% (Calcd. 20.03). Decomposition point : > 300 °C.

The same compound was also prepared following the aforementioned procedure in the presence of nitrite (*tris*-B) or nitrate (*tris*-C) bases. The elemental analyses of these two reveal almost same result as *tris*-A. The decomposition temperature of these two is somewhat less than *tris*-A. Decomposition point : 292 °C (*tris*-B) and 277 °C (*tris*-C).

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Tris-complex, Na[Ni(acac)₃] was synthesized and isolated from the starting material, *trans*-Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂ in methanol-water mixture in presence of azide (*tris*-A), nitrite (*tris*-B) or nitrate (*tris*-C) base. The complex obtained by using different bases separately is assigned as mentioned in parenthesis with an endeavor to optimize the process of synthesis, i.e. to find out the suitable base for the synthesis. These *tris*-A, *tris*-B and *tris*-C are insoluble in non-polar solvents and are partially soluble in common polar organic solvents, such as EtOH, MeCN and Me₂CO, but highly soluble in water and DMF.

Molar conductivity of the *tris*-complex :

The molar conductance values of all the complexes, *tris*-A, *tris*-B and *tris*-C were determined using the fol-

lowing eq. (1) instantly using a conductivity meter of a millimolar solution of complexes in water at 25 °C.

$$\Lambda_M = 1000\kappa/C \quad (1)$$

where Λ_M = molar conductivity, κ = specific conductance and C = concentration (mol/dm³). The molar conductivity values of these complexes are summarized in Table 1. The molar conductivity values measured after immediate dissolutions of *tris*-A, *tris*-B, and *tris*-C are 98, 95, and 88 S cm² mol⁻¹, respectively indicating they are 1 : 1 electrolyte whereas *trans*-Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂ is found to be non-electrolyte. The molar conductivity values of our synthesized complexes are electrolyte in nature and quite different from all reported purely acac-complexes of nickel(II) : square planar mononuclear, Ni(acac)₂, octahedral trinuclear, Ni₃(acac)₆ and dinuclear, Ni₂(acac)₂(H₂O)₂ those are non-electrolyte. It is noteworthy to mention that in the course of measurement the conductivity value (κ) increases with time. This phenomenon suggests that there may be the presence of polymeric chain of interaction as shown in Scheme 1 between Na⁺ cations and complex ions [Na(acac)₃]⁻ which was demonstrated by Baldo *et al.*¹⁹ in its crystal structure report. The reason of increasing conductivity may be the release of Na⁺ ions from the polymeric chain, consequently increasing mobility of Na⁺ ions.

UV-Vis spectroscopy study :

UV-Vis spectroscopy is an important tool to determine the geometry of a complex, especially, Ni^{II}-complexes and the study of effects of substituents on it. Fig. 1 shows the UV-Vis spectra of isolated products obtained

Scheme 1. Polymeric chain of Na[Ni(acac)₃] units.

Table 1. Molar conductivities of complexes

Compd.	Λ_M (molar conductivity) (S cm ² mol ⁻¹)
<i>trans</i> -[Ni ^{II} (acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	20
<i>tris</i> -A	98
<i>tris</i> -B	95
<i>tris</i> -C	88

from the starting material *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] in the presence of azide (*tris*-A) (Fig. 1a), nitrite (*tris*-B) (Fig. 1b), and nitrate (*tris*-C) (Fig. 1c) along with *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] (Fig. 1d) and [Ni(H₂O)₆]²⁺ (Fig. 1e). All spectra were recorded in water instantaneously. Ni^{II} has *d*⁸-configuration with ³*F*, ¹*D*, ³*P* – the three successive spectroscopic energy terms. Under the ligand field effect ³*F* splits into ³*A*_{2g}, ³*T*_{2g} and ³*T*_{1g}; ¹*D* into ¹*E*_g and ³*P* into ³*T*_{1g}. Thus, there would be three of four spin allowed transition ³*A*_{2g}(³*F*)→³*T*_{2g}(³*F*) (*v*₁); ³*A*_{2g}(³*F*)→³*T*_{1g}(³*F*) (*v*₂); ³*A*_{2g}(³*F*)→³*T*_{1g}(³*P*) (*v*₃) and one spin-forbidden transition, ³*A*_{2g}(³*F*)→¹*E*_g(¹*D*) (*v*₄) possible in case of an octahedral complex. In the case of Ni^{II} octahedral complexes, the difference in energy between the two lowest energy terms, the ³*A*_{2g} and ³*T*_{2g} is equal to Δ₀. Therefore, to find Δ₀, we simply find the energy of the lowest-energy transition in the absorption spectrum. The spectrum of [Ni(H₂O)₆]²⁺ (Fig. 1e) exhibit four absorption bands corresponding to *v*₁, *v*₂, *v*₃, and *v*₄. Resembling other chelate complexes of Ni^{II}, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and *tris*-A–*tris*-C show three absorption bands corresponds to *v*₁, *v*₂, and *v*₃, where *v*₃ is a

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of (a) Na[Ni(acac)₃] (*tris*-A); (b) Na[Ni(acac)₃] (*tris*-B); (c) Na[Ni(acac)₃] (*tris*-C); (d) *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺; (e) [Ni(H₂O)₆]²⁺.

very intense band and couldn't show in the Fig. 1. The spectral features evidences that these are having octahedral geometry. The UV-Vis absorption bands along with their assignment are tabulated in the Table 2. The appearance of the spin-forbidden *v*₄ band which is very prominent only in the hexa-aquo nickel(II), [Ni(H₂O)₆]²⁺ complex ion is due to the spin-orbit coupling that mixes the ³*T*_{1g}(*F*) and ¹*E*_g states²². Upon treatment of hot methanolic solution of *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] with various inorganic bases : N₃⁻, NO₂⁻, or NO₃⁻ led to the formation of solid product *tris*-A–C, immediately. The

Table 2. UV-Vis spectral data and assignment of band positions

Complex	λ , nm (ϵ)	<i>v</i> ₁ (³ <i>A</i> _{2g} → ³ <i>T</i> _{2g}) (cm ⁻¹)	<i>v</i> ₄ (³ <i>A</i> _{2g} → ¹ <i>E</i> _g) (cm ⁻¹)	<i>v</i> ₂ (³ <i>A</i> _{2g} → ³ <i>T</i> _{1g} (<i>F</i>)) (cm ⁻¹)	<i>v</i> ₃ (³ <i>A</i> _{2g} → ³ <i>T</i> _{1g} (<i>P</i>)) (cm ⁻¹)
[Ni(H ₂ O) ₆] ²⁺	1176, 740, 649, 395	8500	13500	15400	25300
[Ni ^{II} (H ₂ O) ₆] ²⁺	719 (0.028), 656 (0.025), 390 (0.073)	Obscured	13908	15244	25641
<i>trans</i> -[Ni ^{II} (acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1084 (0.038), 741sh (0.018), 633 (0.042), ~ 334	9225	13495	15798	Obscured
<i>tris</i> -A	1062 (0.021), 739sh (0.024), 623 (0.042), ~ 334	9416	13531	16051	Obscured
<i>tris</i> -B	1062 (0.037), 739 (0.026), 626 (0.048)	9416	13531	15974	Obscured
<i>tris</i> -C	1074 (0.040), 743sh (0.035), 632 (0.052), ~ 334	9311	13459	15823	Obscured

spectral features of *tris-A-tris-C* are quite same, unsymmetrical ($I(\nu_2) \gg I(\nu_1)$; I = intensity of absorbance) and different from the starting material, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] which is symmetrical ($I(\nu_2) \sim I(\nu_1)$) in nature. The most noticeable point is that the absorption maxima of all bands are blue shifted especially, ν_1 bands. Comparing band features and blue shifting of ν_1 bands of *tris-A-tris-C* with *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂], it is evident that the *tris-A-tris-C* are almost identical complex and totally different from the starting complex, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂]. There are three possibilities : these may be (i) the adducts of corresponding bases, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(X)₂] (where X = N₃⁻, NO₂⁻, or NO₃⁻); or (ii) the dimer, [Ni₂(acac)₄(H₂O)₂] or trimer, [Ni₃(acac)₆]; or (iii) the homoleptic *tris*-anion, [Ni(acac)₃]⁻. IR spectral studies of *tris-A-tris-C* which will be discussed in the next section, do not show any peak characteristic of the added bases, ruling out the possibility-(i). Instantaneous measurement of conductance, estimation of nickel per acac, and elemental analysis gave the preliminary evidences about the reckoning of complex composition with possibility-(iii) and ruled out the possibility-(ii). Baldo *et al.*¹⁹ obtained [Na{Ni(acac)₃}]_n as a secondary product of a synthesis carried out at room temperature, where Na(acac)₂, L-histidine, sodium *tert*-butoxide and sodium azide were mixed in a 3 : 2 : 3 : 3 molar ratio, using methanol as solvent. The product was isolated as crystals with very low yield (15%) from the solution of reaction mixture after three weeks. They studied solid UV-Vis spectrum and observed a weak band at 625 nm (16000 cm⁻¹) along with very intense band below 350 nm. Our prepared *tris-A* and *B* exhibit strong absorption bands at 623 and 626 nm, respectively whereas *tris-C* shows at 633 nm along with other bands like *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and can be treated as a *tris*-anionic complex as shown in Scheme 1. It is noteworthy to mention that Atencio *et al.*¹⁸ reported the crystal structure of K[Ni(acac)₃].0.3H₂O, a potassium salt of *tris*-anionic complex of nickel(II)-acetylacetonate.

IR spectroscopic study :

The infrared absorption spectra of *trans*-[Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂] (Fig. 2A), azide assisted-*tris-A* (Fig.

2B), nitrite assisted-*tris-B* (Fig. 2C) and nitrate assisted-*tris-C* (Fig. 2D) are shown in Fig. 2. The IR absorption bands for the complexes, together with their assignments, are reported in the Table 3. The absence of characteristic peak of N₃⁻, NO₂⁻ or NO₃⁻ in their corresponding spectrum is ruled out the formation of adducts rather it is a base assisted conversion of *trans*-[Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂] complex to *tris*-complex, Na[Ni(acac)₃] or Na[Ni(acac)₃].H₂O. The starting neutral complex, *trans*-[Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂] (Fig. 2A) exhibits a very strong and broad band centered at 3396 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ vibrations of the coordinated water molecules and of their hydrogen bonded groups along with $\nu(\text{CH})$. The band is almost absent from the spectrum of *tris*-complex, *tris-A* (Fig. 2B) or *tris-B* (Fig. 2C), indicating the absence of coordinated water molecules in these complexes. The low-intense broad band at 3400 cm⁻¹ of each of these spectra may be attributed to the stretching frequency of $\nu(\text{CH})$. The intensity and broadness of the band is reduced remarkably and appeared quite blue shifted ($\Delta\nu = 28 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 3426 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of *tris-C* (Fig. 2D). The reason may be due to the present of hydrated water molecules in this complex. The spectrum of *trans*-[Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂] exhibits well defined bands at about 1606 and 1517 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$, which are slightly coupled, and at 1448 cm⁻¹ due to $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ (where δ is in-plane bending mode)²³⁻²⁶. These bands especially, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in the spectra for the complexes *tris-A-tris-C* red-shifts to 1590 cm⁻¹ in comparison with that for the starting *trans*-complex. The red-shifting of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ reveals the strengthening of the Ni-O(acac) bonds and weakening of the -C=O bonds. The asymmetric CH-bending (in-plane) of CH₃ assigned as $\delta(\text{CH}_3)$ for the *trans*-complex at 1448 cm⁻¹ is expected to shift to lower frequency ($\sim 1404 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for the *tris*-complex as a result of experiencing more unsaturation of the neighboring carbon atom and the α -carbonyl group. The band at about 1260 cm⁻¹ is in accordance with symmetric C-C-C stretch mixed with the symmetric deformation of the -CH₃ groups. The out-of-plane rocking modes of the -CH₃ groups appear at 1017 cm⁻¹. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{CH}_3)$ stretching frequency appears in the spectra at about 922 cm⁻¹. These three bands :

Fig. 2. IR spectra of (A) $trans\text{-}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$; (B) $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ (*tris*-A); (C) $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ (*tris*-B); (D) $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3].x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (*tris*-C).

Table 3. Infrared (IR) spectral data of complexes and their assignment

$trans\text{-}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ν (cm^{-1})	$\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ (<i>tris</i> -A) ν (cm^{-1})	$\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ (<i>tris</i> -B) ν (cm^{-1})	$\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3].\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (<i>tris</i> -C) ν (cm^{-1})	Assignment
3396	3400	3400	3426	$\nu\text{C-H}$
1606	1590	1590	1591	νCO
1517 vs	1515 vs	1515 vs	1517 vs	$\nu(\text{C-C-C})$
1448 s, br	1404 s, br	1404.00 s, br	1404 s, br	$\delta(\text{CH}_3)$
1262 s	1260 s	1261 s	1261 s	$\nu(\text{C-C-C})_{\text{Sm}}$
1196 w	1196 w	1196 w	1197 w	$\beta(\text{C-H})$
1125	1121	1119	1123	πCH_3
1021 m-w	1017 m-w	1017 m-w	1018 m-w	πCH_3
926 m	922 m	922 m	925 m	C-CH_3
764 m	772 m	772 m	771 m	γCH (olefinic)
656 m-w	658 m-w	658 m-w	659 m-w	$\delta(\text{ring})$
584	566	566	567	$\delta(\text{ring}) + \pi\text{CH}_3$
427 m-w	–	433 m-w	–	$\beta(\text{C-CH}_3)$

β = in-plane bending mode; δ = deformation mode; γ = out-of-plane bending mode; ν = stretching mode; π = rocking mode; Sm = symmetric; vs = very strong; w = weak; m = medium; s = strong.

about 1260, 1017, and 922 cm^{-1} of all the *tris*-complexes are observed in the IR spectra without much shifting. The band at 764 cm^{-1} which is assigned as $\pi(\text{C-H})^{27}$ involving vinyl C-H hydrogen wagging out-of-plane of acac-ligand for the *trans*-complex is blue shifted to 772 cm^{-1} for *tris*-complex, indicating more planarity. It has been demonstrated theoretically and experimentally by Baker *et al.*²⁷. Another evidence for such acac-chelate ring planarity is incurred from the ring deformation along with $\pi(\text{CH}_3 \text{ rocking})$ band value which appears at 566 cm^{-1} for *tris*-complexes, 18 cm^{-1} red shifted in comparison with *trans*-bis-complex (584 cm^{-1}). A characteristic band at about 427 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$. In contrast, the products obtained from the treatment of *trans*-[Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂] with bases : N_3^- , NO_2^- or NO_3^- show blue shifted two equally splitting bands at about 433 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to strong Ni-O(acac) bonds. The UV-Vis spectral feature has given the preliminary support to our supposition. Now, the IR data evident that the *tris*-A and B may have the composition like $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]^{19}$ and the *tris*-C having water molecules can be formulated as $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}^{18}$.

Stability of complexes in acid medium :

The stability of the as-synthesized *tris*-complex, $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ or $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and *trans*-[Ni(acac)(H₂O)₂] was studied in acid medium as well as in aqueous solution spectrophotometrically. A representative spectral change along with the graphical plots of pH vs wavelength of absorption maxima is shown in Fig. 3. The intensity of absorption maxima in aqueous solution of *tris*-A, *tris*-B or *tris*-C is decreased with time. The spectral changes for the *tris*-A complex in aqueous solution is shown in Fig. 3A as a representative one. The spectra changes show that the *tris*-complex is unstable in water with $k_{\text{obs}} = 4.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and gets aquated to its *trans*-diaquo-complex (Fig. 3A). The starting material, *trans*-complex on the other hand, is stable in aqueous solution (UV-Vis spectrum is not shown in the figure). The stability of the *tris*-complex obtained from different inorganic base assisted paths and the *trans*-isomer, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] have been studied separately in different pH media. The absorption spectra of the *trans*-complex (Fig. 3B) and *tris*-A (Fig. 3C) in different pH

values are also shown in the Fig. 3, as a representative one. Base assisted synthesized *tris*-complexes are susceptible to dissociate in acid media so does the *trans*-complex. In acidic medium whether it *tris*- or *trans*-complex finally dissociates to the aquo-species, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ which is evident from the Fig 3B (d) or 3C (d). In comparison with that for the spectra of *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ it is observed that each *tris*-product (Fig. 3C) with the decrease of pH values dissociates initially into the aquo-form of it, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and which dissociates further with decrease of pH into purely aquated Ni^{II} complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. Thus, it is important to determine the optimum dissociation pH values upon which each base assisted *tris*-product, converts to neutral *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] and then finally to $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. The wavelength of each *tris*-complex is red-shifted with the decrease of pH values. To determine the optimum dissociation pH we apply linear regression equation in between the two variables, wavelength (λ_{max}) and pH and verified the correlation co-efficient (R^2) values. The plots of wavelengths versus pH values are shown in Fig. 3D [Fig. (i) for *trans*-complex; (ii) for *tris*-A, (iii) for *tris*-B, and (iv) for *tris*-C]. Obtained values of optimum dissociation pH and R^2 of all complexes are given in the Table 4.

The R^2 values are nearly one, indicating the linear relationship between wavelength and pH.

$$\text{pH} = -p\lambda_{\text{max}} + q \quad (2)$$

The optimum pH values were calculated from the equation using corresponding wavelength. The dissociation pH values are also revealed the stability order of the *tris*-complex in the acid medium as *tris*-A > *tris*-B > *tris*-C. Inspection of the dissociation pH values (Table 4) of the *tris*-complex obtained by the assistance of different bases clearly indicate that the azide assisted *tris*-complex, $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ (*tris*-A) is the most stable one. Thus, azide might be the best base to be employed for this purpose. At pH 1.50, *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] dissociates into the aquo-complex of Ni^{II}.

Dissociation kinetics :

The kinetics of the dissociation reactions of the *tris*-[Ni(acac)₃]⁻ complex ion (*tris*-A) and *trans*-

Fig. 3. UV-Vis spectra of (A) Na[Ni(acac)₃] in water at different time interval; (B) *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] at different pH : (a) pH 3, (b) pH 2.3, (c) pH 2, (d) pH 1.3; (C) Na[Ni(acac)₃] (*tris*-A), at different pH : (a) pH 3, (b) pH 2.3, (c) pH 2, (d) pH 1.3, (e) *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] in water (B and C), (f) [Ni(H₂O)₆]²⁺ and a plot of (D) pH vs wavelength : (i) *trans*-[Ni^{II}(acac)₂(H₂O)₂], (ii) [Ni^{II}(acac)₃]⁻ (*tris*-A), (iii) [Ni^{II}(acac)₃]⁻ (*tris*-B), and (iv) [Ni^{II}(acac)₃]⁻ (*tris*-C).

Table 4. Optimum pH values of transformation

pH and R ² / Complexes	<i>trans</i> - [Ni(acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	<i>tris</i> -A	<i>tris</i> -B	<i>tris</i> -C
pH at λ _{max} = 633	-	2.16	2.35	2.52
nm of <i>trans</i> -isomer				
pH at λ _{aquo} = 656	1.50	0.77	1.02	1.28
nm of aquo complex				
Correlation co-efficient (R ²)	0.95	0.93	0.99	0.93

[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂] were studied at 25 °C, with I = 0.2 mol/dm³ (HCl + NaCl), and in 0.001–0.05 mol/dm³ HCl solution. The dissociation rate equations of *trans*-aquo and *tris*-complex are given in eqs. (3) and (4), respectively.

$$-d[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]^-/dt = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]^- \quad (3)$$

$$-d[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]/dt = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] \quad (4)$$

The dissociation reactions of these complexes were found to be completed, and the observed pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}, of the complexes are determined from the

Table 5. Kinetic data with rate constants in the acid-dissociation of the complexes at 25 °C

Complexes	[H ⁺] (M)	<i>k</i> _{obs}	<i>K</i> _{H⁺}	<i>k</i> _s × 10 ³
<i>tris</i> -[Ni(acac) ₃] ⁻	0.001	0.028	6.56	2.0
	0.005	0.022		
	0.01	0.058		
	0.05	0.333		
<i>trans</i> -[Ni(acac) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	0.001	0.0403	10.89	5.7
	0.005	0.0252		
	0.01	0.1215		
	0.05	0.552		

plots of -ln (A_t - A_a) vs time; a representative graph for the *tris*-complex is given in Fig. 4 (Fig. 4A-D: with [H⁺] = 0.001 (A), 0.005 (B), 0.01 (C) and 0.05 (D) mol/dm³, respectively) and data for the both complexes : *tris*-complex and *trans*-diaquo-complex (graphical plots are not included) are given in Table 5. The kinetic data presented in the Table 5, clearly indicate that the observed pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs} values are increasing rapidly with increasing hydrogen ion concen-

Fig. 4. Plots of $-\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ vs time, min of the complex, Na[Ni(acac)₃] (*tris-A*) (A) $[H^+] = 0.001$ mol/dm³; (B) $[H^+] = 0.005$ mol/dm³; (C) $[H^+] = 0.01$ mol/dm³; (D) $[H^+] = 0.05$ mol/dm³ and plots of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$, M for (E) [Ni(acac)₃]⁻ and (F) *trans*-[Ni(acac)₂(H₂O)₂].

tration, i.e. decreasing pH. It reveals the acid catalyzing hydrolysis. A proposed mechanism of dissociation of complexes is shown in the Scheme 2.

The plots of k_{obs} versus $[H^+]$ (Figs. 4E and 4F) are linear with slight positive intercepts and

$$k_{obs} = k_s + K_H^+[H^+] \quad (5)$$

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanistic steps of dissociation of (A) $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]^-$ and (B) $\text{trans-Ni}(\text{acac})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$.

can be fitted with eq. (5). Where K_{H^+} and k_s are the protonation equilibrium and dissociation or solvation constants, respectively. K_{H^+} can be expressed by the eq. (6) for *tris*-complex and eq. (7) for

$$K_{\text{H}^+} = K_{1\text{H}^+} K_{2\text{H}^+} K_{3\text{H}^+} / K_{-1\text{H}^+} K_{-2\text{H}^+} K_{-3\text{H}^+} \quad (6)$$

$$K_{\text{H}^+} = K_{1\text{H}^+} K_{2\text{H}^+} / K_{-1\text{H}^+} K_{-2\text{H}^+} \quad (7)$$

the *trans*-complex. The values of K_{H^+} and k_s were calculated by linear least-square analyses from the slope and intercept of k_{obs} versus $[\text{H}^+]$ as shown in the Figs. 4E and 4F and are included in the Table 5. Inspection of the data clearly indicates that the *trans*-diaquo-complex (Fig. 4F) is far less stable and more prone to dissociate than the *tris*-complex (*tris*-A, Fig. 4E) in acidic media. The added stability of the *tris*-complex may be due to the presence of three acac ligands without having any coordinated water.

Conclusions

A systematic inorganic base assisted synthetic method of preparation and isolation of sodium salt of *tris*-(acetylacetonato)nickelate(II), $\text{Na}[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_3]$ has been established. The complex is 1 : 1 electrolyte. The characteristic feature of UV-Vis spectra of the *tris*-complex is that the intensity of ν_2 band is much higher than that of ν_1 band and quite different from all of the reported Ni-acac complexes. The stability of it in aqueous as well as in acidic media has been studied. The complex is susceptible to dissociate in aqueous medium ($k_{\text{obs}} = 4.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) as well as in acid media ($k_s = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$). Moreover, the stability of the *tris*-complex in acid-media is far greater than that of the *trans*-complex. Thus, to comprehend the potentiality of Ni^{II} -complexes of

acetylacetonate, the as-synthesized *tris*-complex would be a futuristic material.

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